

Determination of Scattering Parameters with Respect to the
Characteristic Impedance of Precision Coaxial Air-Line Standards
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Abstract

Scattering parameter expressions with respect to the characteristic impedances in correspondence to the principal mode are developed for the coaxial air-line standard. Dimensional variations of the inner and outer conductors and skin effect loss are included in the model. The local characteristic impedance, which is found from the stored energy principle, is derived from the forward and backward voltage and current waves of the principal mode. Four sources of error for $|S_{11}|$ are discussed.

Introduction

Precision coaxial air-line standards play a central role as reference standard devices in automatic network analyzer measurements. To accurately characterize the coaxial air-line standard for the principal mode (TEM mode with axial (z) dependence), it is necessary to consider imperfections due to skin effect and surface roughness. Skin effects of conducting surfaces are now well documented and variations from inner and outer conductor dimensions throughout the coaxial air line can be measured to resolutions of $\pm 0.254 \mu\text{m}$. When a high precision dimensional measurement system probes a nominally uniform air-line conductor surface, the two-port device evolves into an unsymmetrical nonuniform air line. Consequently, the characteristic impedance is no longer independent of position and direction of propagation.

The purpose of this paper is to determine the scattering parameters with respect to the characteristic impedance of precision coaxial air line. To accomplish this goal, the forward and backward wave solutions, which depend on the axial variable z , superimpose to form the principal mode EM field. Hence, for each terminal plane of the nonuniform air line, a reference characteristic impedance which is dependent on integration of the local parameters $L(z)$, $C(z)$, and $R(z)$ over the length of the air line is defined. Hence, the global (or total) line parameters L , R , and C are valid only for a particular terminal plane. Modeling accuracy for the scattering parameters and characteristic impedance is shown to be primarily dependent on conductor radius measurement precision.

Principal Mode Parameters

In a previous paper [1], the axial (z) dependence of the radial electric field and the angular magnetic field for the principal mode of the coaxial air line were established. Two coupled generalized telegraphist equations for the principal mode voltage ($V_{00}(z)$) and current ($I_{00}(z)$) were found (the z dependent components of the fields E_r and H_ϕ).

Using the generalized telegraphist equations as a starting point, four coupled Volterra type integral equations representing forward and backward waves for voltage and current are found. Equivalently, the voltage and current waves are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} V_{00}(z) &= V_{00}^+(z) + V_{00}^-(z) \\ \text{and} \quad I_{00}(z) &= I_{00}^+(z) - I_{00}^-(z) \end{aligned}$$

With respect to terminal plane 1 (TP1), forward propagation occurs from TP1 to TP2 while reflected propagation occurs from TP2 to TP1.

At this point the local inductance $L(z)$, capacitance $C(z)$, and resistance $R(z)$ are defined as functions of $V_{00}^+(z)$, $V_{00}^-(z)$, $I_{00}^+(z)$, and $I_{00}^-(z)$ from the stored energy concept [2]. Setting $k = 1$ or $k = 2$ and exciting the air line at terminal plane k produces global line parameters L_{ok} , C_{ok} , and R_{ok} , and subsequently, the characteristic impedance Z_{ok} . The scattering parameters with respect to Z_{01} and Z_{02} numerically satisfy the reciprocity and physical realizability principles.

The variation of $|S_{11}|$ with respect to the characteristic impedance Z_{01} for a 7 mm air line 15.7 cm in length with a frequency range of 1 to 18 GHz is illustrated below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. $|S_{11}|$ with respect to Z_{01} from 1 to 18 GHz.

The measurement planes for the radial measurements were selected at 1.15 mm intervals near both ends of the air line and 2.50 mm intervals elsewhere. A complete profile of radial measurements of this air line is illustrated in Figure 2 of reference [1]. In conclusion, four principal error sources of $|S_{11}|$ are discussed:

- (1) Surface roughness profiles from air line fabrication,
- (2) Probe measurement precision,
- (3) Increasing eccentricity of the center conductor along the z axis,
- (4) Out of roundness of the outer and/or inner conductor.

References

1. Holt, D. R. Scattering Parameters Representing Imperfections in Precision Coaxial Air Lines, J. of Res., Nat. Inst. Stand. Tech., v. 94, no. 2, Mar.-Apr. 1989.
2. Collin, R. E. Foundations for Microwave Engineering, McGraw-Hill, New York (1966), p.80.